

Groupwise elastic registration by a new sparsity-promoting metric: application to the alignment of cardiac magnetic resonance perfusion images

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Abstract—This paper proposes a methodology for the joint alignment of a sequence of images based on a groupwise registration procedure by using a new family of metrics that exploit the expected sparseness of the temporal intensity curves corresponding to the aligned points. Therefore, this methodology is able to tackle the alignment of temporal sequences of images in which the represented phenomenon varies in time. Specifically, we have applied it to the correction of motion in contrast-enhanced first-pass perfusion cardiac magnetic resonance images. The time sequence is elastically registered as a whole by using the aforementioned family of multi-image metrics and jointly optimizing the parameters of the transformations involved. The proposed metrics are able to cope with dynamic changes in the intensity content of corresponding points in the sequence guided by the assumption that these changes allow for a sparse representation in a properly selected frame. Results have shown the statistically significant improvement in performance of the proposed metric with respect to previous groupwise registration metrics for the problem at hand, which is especially relevant in order to correct for elastic deformations.

Index Terms—Groupwise elastic registration, registration metric, sparseness, cardiac magnetic resonance, myocardial perfusion

1 INTRODUCTION

IMAGE registration is concerned with the search of an optimal transformation for the alignment between objects in (at least) two images. It has many applications in imaging, such as fusion of image information, population modeling and alignment of time-dependent studies [1], which is the application domain that we focus on in this paper. In this case a given phenomenon is studied over time so that corresponding locations have to be found in a temporal collection of images. For instance, in medical imaging time-dependent studies include the deformation of a continuum body, the development of a given pathology, or the passage of a fluid across a region. In these situations, the objective is usually to jointly align a set of more than two images, the information content of corresponding points could vary among different images due to temporal changes in the imaged features and different types of transformations could be involved in the misalignment to be corrected. This paper proposes

a methodology for the alignment of contrast-enhanced first-pass perfusion cardiac magnetic resonance (MR) images (hereafter *cardiac MR perfusion images*). Nevertheless, the proposed methodology (or a simpler form of it) is generally applicable to most registration problems in time-dependent studies. Thus, although in this paper we are going to refer to its application to the alignment of cardiac MR perfusion images, it can be considered a generic methodology for a relatively broad spectrum of registration problems.

Cardiac MR perfusion images require the injection of a contrast agent that, when uptaken by a given tissue, shortens the T_1 relaxation time of the tissue and thus the intensity of the signal increases in the case that a T_1 -weighted image sequence is used. In its application to cardiac images, this technique provides information about the myocardial blood supply, which might be an indicator of myocardial ischemia [2]. The alignment of these images is a necessary prior step for a precise regional analysis of the temporal curves of contrast uptake in the myocardium, since patient breathing causes misalignments among the images of the acquired time sequence. Moreover, if diaphragmatic navigators are used to prospectively correct for breath motion, there is usually a residual non-rigid displacement associated with inaccuracies in the electrocardiogram (ECG) triggering, the non-uniform component of the breath deformation or other motion-related artifacts [3]. If the patient is able

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Fig. 1. Perfusion alignment problem. The figure on the right shows the mean perfusion curves in three of the six standard zones of the myocardium shown on the left. We include the original curves and the curves after applying the alignment method proposed in this paper. The original curves present more variability than the aligned curves. In some cases the appearance of both curves is completely different (for instance see the curves corresponding to zone 5), which supports the key role of the alignment. The remaining oscillations in the curves after the alignment can be mainly attributed to image noise.

to collaborate, breath-holding can be tried to facilitate correspondence, but this is only possible in a relatively small interval of the total acquisition duration (usually around the first passage of the contrast through the heart), with an abrupt change in the position of the heart when the patient suddenly breaths. Needless to say, manual correction of breath-derived misalignments is also possible but it is time consuming and subject to inter- and intra-operator variability. We show an illustration of the influence of the alignment on perfusion curves in Fig. 1.

According to [1], image registration involves three main components, (i) a deformation model, (ii) an objective function, and (iii) an optimization strategy. For the specific problem of myocardial alignment in cardiac MR perfusion images, three corresponding issues should be borne in mind:

- A rigid registration is not enough in practice to correct for breathing motion. The most convincing reason is the existence of transversal motion¹, but an imprecise ECG-gating and other artifacts are also usual in practice. Therefore non-rigid or elastic registration procedures seem preferable.
- Perfusion images in two different time instants have different intensity information. Thus monomodal registration techniques may not be optimal and attention should be paid to multimodal solutions². Therefore it seems critical to construct a robust

1. It should be taken into account that though some recent works have proposed feasible 3D cardiac perfusion acquisition techniques [4], most common protocols still used in the clinical practice only acquire three short axis images corresponding to the basal, the medial and the apical zones, so that there is not enough image information to recover from longitudinal rigid motion.

2. In this paper we refer to *multimodal* registration as the one that considers the possibility of intensity changes at corresponding points in different images (regardless of whether the underlying physics of the scanning procedure is the same for different images or not).

metric to measure misalignment among the images (even more considering the localized nature of the fidelity measures in the elastic registration case).

- The objective is to align the whole sequence. Therefore the procedure could benefit from adopting a global perspective in its formulation, which will in turn influence the optimization strategy to be applied.

In the present work, we propose a methodology that tackles these three issues. First we pose the problem as a multiresolution³ elastic groupwise registration one. This way, we model any kind of relative deformation among the images and consider the problem as a whole. Subsequently, we develop a new metric for the groupwise alignment of dynamic temporal data, i.e., when temporal changes of the intensity of a given point are expected to occur. The basic assumption of our metric is that this temporal curve has a sparse nature and thus can be expressed by a small number of coefficients in a properly selected frame. According to this assumption, our metric will measure the sparseness of the temporal curves derived from the images.

The paper is structured as follows: in Section 2 we analyze the precedents of our work together with the existing literature on the alignment of cardiac MR perfusion images. Section 3 presents the simultaneous or groupwise registration formulation together with some existing alternatives for the choice of the metric in this scenario. In Section 4 we introduce the new family of metrics proposed in this paper; therefore this Section contains the major contribution of our work. Details on the application of the proposed methodology to cardiac MR perfusion alignment are given in Section 5. Later on, in Section 6, the method is extensively validated by justifying the adopted methodology against previous approaches and by studying its sensitivity with respect to different parameter configurations and design choices. The major implications and possibilities of generalization of the proposed methodology along with its possible application domains are outlined in Section 7 to end up with some conclusions in Section 8.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Precedents of the work

As [6] pointed out, most intensity-based similarity measures, such as the mean squared error (MS), the normalized correlation (NC) or the mutual information (MI) are defined directly on image intensities without considering their spatial dependencies. Thus a random simultaneous shuffle of pixel positions in the images does not change these measures. This property translates to most groupwise registration metrics (which are constructed as extensions of the classic pairwise counterparts) as in this case the ordering of the set of images to be

3. The use of a multiresolution strategy should not be considered as nuclear in our formulation. It only serves to help the optimization escape from local optima and to potentially accelerate the algorithm [5].

registered does not influence the metric. However this effect is undesirable for time-dependent studies, where the temporal relationship of the phenomena to be measured should be taken into account in the metric. In a manner similar to that proposed by [6] for considering spatial nonstationarities or distortions, we propose to use a measure of the complexity of the temporal curves as the basis for the construction of the objective function of registration. However, our approach is different from the one adopted by [6] in that our metric construction is directly based on functional analysis. Specifically, the authors of [6] derived the metric by trying to favor a smooth residual intensity correction image (which accounts for the remaining differences between the images once they are registered), so they resorted to a cosine transform based metric (a derivative-based regularizer). Unlike them, we make direct use of the wavelet transform theory to build the metric since we try to model scenarios in which abrupt changes of intensity are possible⁴ so that Fourier analysis does not seem appropriate.

Metric definition for groupwise registration has been an active area of research since the introduction of this framework. For a review of different possibilities see [7], [8]. As mentioned before, most proposed metrics are extensions of the pairwise metrics to the groupwise case. We will review some of these extensions in Section 3. Nevertheless, specially in time-dependent studies, we understand that groupwise metrics should have a different conception; for time-ordered problems, more flexibility could be obtained if the relative position of different images in the sequence has a direct influence on the metric, i.e., if intensity disparities contribute differently to the objective function depending on the temporal position of the images. As far as we know this kind of assumption has never been applied before for groupwise registration in time-dependent studies. Motivated by these ideas, in this paper we resort to wavelet analysis, a powerful approach to describe and characterize different types of temporal signals even in the presence of discontinuities, in order to balance the contributions of the image disparities to the registration metric.

2.2 State of the art in the alignment of perfusion sequences

Automatic alignment of perfusion sequences has been performed by very different approaches. Thus in [9] a multiresolution registration procedure is proposed, which is based on a 2D rigid transformation as well as on a MS metric. The method is rigorously validated and the authors emphasize the stability of this metric for dealing with rotations. Nevertheless, the metric chosen seems to be valid in terms of the mean error of the procedure as a whole, but may be less appropriate in

the specific instants when the injected contrast reaches the tissues of interest, which are in turn the instants in which the registration should be more accurate so that accurate perfusion measures may be obtained accordingly. This problem has been further discussed in [10]. Similar considerations can be made with regard to the proposal in [11], which uses the NC metric, also suited for monomodal registration.

The method described in [12] makes use of the normalized MI. This paper employs a multiresolution approach as well as a discrete deformation space to get rid of local minima. Though the methodology seems better suited for the analysis of this type of images, posing the problem as a rigid and pairwise registration is prone to the presence of outliers in the alignment, as we pointed out in Section 1.

Some methods proposed in the literature depart from the rigid motion assumption indicated above. This is of special relevance in the case that images are acquired at end systole, a phase in which the heart motion is larger so it may be more difficult to obtain a precise gating. Additionally, if arrhythmias are present, a precise gating could be very difficult to achieve. One of these methods has been recently proposed in [13]. In this paper, the adopted metric combines information derived from the gradient orientation and the intensity of the images. The quasi-periodicity of the breathing pattern is also considered and smooth solutions are favored.

Fewer attempts have been performed to align the whole perfusion sequence simultaneously. Most of them construct a reference sequence which is supposed to be free of motion and is obtained either by principal or independent component analysis [14], [15], [16] or by the introduction of spatio-temporal constraints [17] and register the perfusion sequence against this reference or template. These methods have proven to be more robust than their pairwise counterparts. However, some heuristics or careful parameter fits are usually needed, which could be an issue in the generalizability of these procedures. Another attempt which does not explicitly use a reference image is described in [18]. This method takes advantage of training the system by the extraction of spatio-temporal statistical features from one template image without respiratory artifacts and pathology. Once more, the construction of this template image could be an issue in practical scenarios and it could introduce a bias in the alignment procedure.

In short, our approach is a simple unsupervised methodology to perform a joint elastic alignment able to cope with temporal intensity changes. Hence, the major drawbacks of the aforementioned references (summarized in Table 1) are avoided.

3 GROUPWISE REGISTRATION

Suppose we are given a set of images $\mathcal{I} = \{I_1, \dots, I_N\}$, with $1 \leq n \leq N$ indexing each of them, $I_n(\mathbf{x}_n)$, which are respectively defined over the space $\mathbf{x}_n \in \mathcal{X}_n \subset \mathbb{E}^L$

4. In cardiac perfusion images abrupt changes will occur when the contrast reaches a given region.

TABLE 1

Main features of the methods proposed for the alignment of perfusion sequences. Gr: Groupwise. MuM: Multimodal. NR: Non-rigid. MuR: Multiresolution. TF: Template-free.

Method	Gr	MuM	NR	MuR	TF
[9]	×	×	×	✓	✓
[10]	×	×	×	✓	✓
[11]	×	×	×	×	✓
[14]	✓	✓	✓	×	×
[12]	×	✓	×	✓	✓
[15]	✓	✓	×	×	×
[13]	×	✓	✓	✓	×
[17]	✓	✓	✓	×	×
[18]	✓	✓	×	×	×
[16]	✓	✓	✓	✓	×
Ours	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of the groupwise registration problem.

with L the dimensionality of the images. As sketched in Fig. 2, the registration problem is stated as that of finding a set of transformations, $\mathcal{T} = \{T_n : \mathbf{x}_n = T_n(\mathbf{x})\}$, from a common reference frame $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{E}^L$ to the space of the images such that a cost function:

$$H(\mathcal{T}) = \int_{\mathcal{X}} V(I_1(T_1(\mathbf{x})), \dots, I_N(T_N(\mathbf{x}))) d\mathbf{x} \quad (1)$$

is minimized. This formulation makes no assumption about the selection of the reference frame. In order to constrain it without giving primacy to any image, one possibility is to restrict the average deformation to be the identity transformation [19]:

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N T_n(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}. \quad (2)$$

The key issues in this formulation are the definition of the metric V and the assumptions on the transformation set \mathcal{T} . Regarding the assumptions on \mathcal{T} , the transformations involved are usually assumed to conform to the same functional form, as the underlying source of geometrical variations among the images is frequently the same. Once the functional form of the transformations is specified, the minimization of (1) in the transformations set is reduced to the minimization in the space of their parameters, which can be performed,

for instance, by a gradient descent procedure which considers the constraint in (2).

The most important metrics proposed in the literature are:

- **Variance of the intensity** [20]:

$$V(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \left(I_n(T_n(\mathbf{x})) - \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n'=1}^N I_{n'}(T_{n'}(\mathbf{x})) \right)^2. \quad (3)$$

This metric is suited for monomodal registration as it implicitly assumes that the pixel intensities are conserved across the set of images.

- **Entropy of the distribution of intensities** [21]:

$$V(\mathbf{x}) = S_{\mathcal{T}}(\mathcal{I}(\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{x}))) \simeq -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \log(p(I_n(T_n(\mathbf{x})))), \quad (4)$$

where $p(I_n(T_n(\mathbf{x})))$ is a Parzen window estimation of the intensity distribution of corresponding pixels—see [22] for details on this approximation—. This metric could serve for multimodal registration as it does not perform a constant intensity assumption for each pixel, but a low entropy distribution of corresponding pixel intensities $S_{\mathcal{T}}$, which is approximated by (4). Therefore this metric favors those solutions in which the corresponding pixels intensities are well-concentrated in the intensity space. Notice that, in this case, large variations of intensity are possible while still maintaining a low value for the metric.

- **Accumulated pairwise estimates** [8]:

$$V(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1, m \neq n}^N f(I_n(T_n(\mathbf{x})), I_m(T_m(\mathbf{x}))), \quad (5)$$

with $f(I_n(T_n(\mathbf{x})), I_m(T_m(\mathbf{x})))$ a disparity function usually established by statistical procedures. The authors prove that, under certain assumptions, this kind of construction reduces to the aforementioned metrics. Nevertheless, this procedure is computationally expensive in the general case, since its complexity is of order $O(N^2)$.

- **Variance of the local entropy** [23]: A metric that depends exclusively on pixelwise intensities leaves out local structure information, which could be crucial in order to robustify the metric behavior, especially in multimodal scenarios. To overcome this limitation of pixelwise metrics, a simple approach has been recently described in [23], where a scalar feature is used to characterize the local structure, namely the local entropy $S_{\mathcal{N}}$, computed from the intensities in a neighborhood of the pixel of interest $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x})$ similarly

to (4)⁵:

$$S_{\mathcal{N}}(\mathbf{I}(\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}))) \simeq -\frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}|} \sum_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x})} p(I(\mathbf{x}')) \log(p(I(\mathbf{x}'))), \quad (6)$$

with $|\mathcal{N}|$ the cardinality of the neighborhood. In [23], the sum of squared differences of the extracted feature is proposed as the registration metric, so in the groupwise approach the local entropies $S_{\mathcal{N}}$ would substitute the image intensities I in (3).

All these metrics are based on the assumption that the relative position of the images in the sequence is interchangeable. In the next Section, we propose a methodology for metric construction that considers the temporal behavior of the curves formed by the intensity values of corresponding pixels in the image stack. In Section 6.2 we compare the aforementioned metrics with ours except for the accumulated pairwise estimates one, which is discarded due to its large computational cost.

4 SPARSITY-PROMOTING METRIC

Let us recall the form of the metric for our problem:

$$V(\mathbf{x}) = V(I_1(T_1(\mathbf{x})), \dots, I_N(T_N(\mathbf{x}))) = V(\mathbf{y}(\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{x}))), \quad (7)$$

with \mathbf{y} denoting a vector of intensities corresponding to the temporal collection of images \mathcal{I} . For the moment, we drop the dependence with \mathcal{T} and study the function $V(\mathbf{y})$. Our assumption is that the vector of corresponding intensities \mathbf{y} is sparse in a properly selected frame. Thus we favor those solutions of \mathbf{y} which are sparse in a frame given by the decomposition matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$, with $M \geq N$. Then, we have that

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{y}. \quad (8)$$

is sparse. Specifically, as discussed in Section 2.1, we assume that, once aligned, the temporal signal is going to be sparse in a given wavelet frame, so that \mathbf{A} represents a wavelet decomposition matrix.

Different possibilities exist for measuring the sparsity of a signal —see [24] for a recent discussion—. One essential requirement in order to insert the sparseness-promoting metric in a conventional registration procedure is that of its differentiability. Additionally, we require the measure to be independent of the norm of the vector \mathbf{z} and the sign of its elements. Then, we are going to define our metric in the variable

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}} = \left(\frac{z_m^2}{\|\mathbf{z}\|_2^2} \right), \quad 1 \leq m \leq M. \quad (9)$$

One possibility is to consider the values of the variable $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$ as a set of probabilities of the presence of the component m in the perfusion signal and to use an entropy measure in order to quantify the diversity of the collection of

events given by the decomposition vector. We choose the Renyi entropy, defined as:

$$V(\tilde{\mathbf{z}}) = \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \log \left(\sum_{m=1}^M \tilde{z}_m^\alpha \right), \quad (10)$$

with α a free parameter. Note that for $\alpha = 0$, V corresponds to the logarithm of the size of the support of $\tilde{\mathbf{z}}$, which is a direct measure of the sparsity of the decomposition⁶. When one relaxes the functional by increasing α , one can continue promoting sparsity and simultaneously have a smoother energy function. As discussed in [25], the limiting point is given by $\alpha = 0.5$ in order to preserve the property of Schur-concavity⁷, a reasonable assumption to measure sparseness.

It is interesting to note that, when using a wavelet decomposition, the proposed metric has a complexity of order $O(N)$ [26] so that it remains competitive with the existing metrics proposed in (3) and (4).

Suppose that each of the transformations T_n can be represented by a set of K parameters θ_k , $1 \leq k \leq K$. Then the registration problem can be cast as that of minimizing the value of the metric over the set of parameters $\theta_{k,n}$. The gradient of the metric is given by:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial \theta_{k,n}}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\partial V}{\partial y_n} \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{\partial y_n}{\partial x_n^l} \frac{\partial x_n^l}{\partial \theta_{k,n}}(\mathbf{x}). \quad (11)$$

The terms inside the summation represent the components of the gradient of the image intensity and the derivatives of the transformation with respect to its parameters. The first term on the right-hand side depends on the specific metric choice and in our case it is given by:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial y_n}(\mathbf{y}) = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\partial V}{\partial z_m} \frac{\partial z_m}{\partial y_n}(\mathbf{y}) = \sum_{m=1}^M A_{mn} \frac{\partial V}{\partial z_m}(\mathbf{y}). \quad (12)$$

Plugging (10) and (9) one has:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial V}{\partial z_k}(\mathbf{z}) &= \frac{1}{1-\alpha} \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\partial \tilde{z}_m^\alpha}{\partial z_k}(\mathbf{z})}{\sum_{m=1}^M \tilde{z}_m^\alpha} \\ &= \frac{\alpha}{(1-\alpha) \sum_{m=1}^M \tilde{z}_m^\alpha} \frac{2z_k}{\|\mathbf{z}\|_2^2} \left(\tilde{z}_k^{\alpha-1} - \sum_{m=1}^M \tilde{z}_m^\alpha \right). \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

In Fig 3 we illustrate the sparsity-promoting feature of the metric.

6. On the other hand, for $\alpha = 1$ the Renyi entropy corresponds to the Shannon entropy.

7. This property is related to the preservation of the Lorentz partial ordering of vectors under the application of a given function on them (see [25] for the details).

5. The form of the expressions in (4) and (6) differ because the entropy approximation has been performed by Parzen window probability estimation in the first case and by histogramming in the second.

Fig. 3. Sparsity-promoting feature of the metric. The figure on the left uses the three curves in Fig. 1. A wavelet decomposition is applied (by using the procedure that will be presented in Section 5) and the distribution of coefficients around zero is plotted. We can observe that the density of coefficients near zero is larger in the aligned case, which implies a rise in the sparsity of the perfusion signal. The figures on the right show the spatial distribution of the metric around the myocardium before (top) and after (bottom) the alignment. The alignment diminishes the value of the metric for most points and generates better defined boundaries as most of the motion has been corrected.

5 APPLICATION TO THE ALIGNMENT OF PERFUSION SEQUENCES

In this Section we describe the specific application of the general framework of registration presented in Sections 3 and 4 to the alignment of cardiac MR perfusion sequences. Conventional first-pass perfusion data used in clinical practice usually consist of a set of three slices obtained respectively at the basal, medial and apical locations of the left ventricle (LV) myocardium. Thus due to the large separation between the acquired slices, each slice is processed separately. Hence the data are considered 2D and therefore $L = 2$ in this case. A sequence of the tissue contrast uptake is generated by repeatedly acquiring one image at the same relative position in the cardiac cycle for each slice. An example is presented in Fig. 4.

The method proceeds in the following steps, which are represented in Fig. 5:

- **Extraction of a region of interest (ROI).** This step is motivated by the necessity of confinement of the information used by the registration procedure to the structures of interest in the image, namely those near the LV myocardium. This paper is not focused on the extraction of the ROI \mathcal{X} so that it is assumed that some previous segmentation of the LV myocardium is available at some point of the perfusion sequence (small modifications of the method in [27] could provide this segmentation) and the ROI is obtained by its dilation with a 2D circular kernel of radius ρ . This dilation is intended to capture enough data information so that the following registration procedure is able to recover

the underlying displacement among the images.

- **Correction of bulk motion.** The bulk motion is the major component of the breath-derived misalignment. A centered rigid 2D transformation is used to correct for this effect. It has five parameters: a center of rotation, a rotation angle and a translation. The starting center of rotation is taken as the center of the previously extracted ROI and the identity transformation is taken as the starting condition. Furthermore, $R = 3$ levels of resolution (subsequently indexed by r) are used in order to better capture large deformations. With regard to the choices specific to our proposed metric, we have resorted to an undecimated wavelet transform (UWT) with a second order Daubechies decomposition and $J = 6$ levels of resolution (therefore $M = 7N$ in this case). The use of the Daubechies wavelet is grounded on its ability to easily represent polynomial signals. Finally, $\alpha = 0.5$, as was motivated in Section 4. An experimental study in order to support these choices is performed in Section 6.4.
- **Correction of elastic motion.** The objective of this step is to correct for desynchronies in the ECG triggering used for the acquisition of the images and for other motion related elastic deformations, for instance the longitudinal breath-derived motion. In this case a B-spline elastic transformation is used to model the deformation [28]. This choice is motivated by the fact that this parametric model of the deformation has been widely used in practice and we are interested in performing the validation mainly with respect to the metric rather than to the transformation design. The bulk transformation obtained in the previous step is used as the starting condition of this registration step. Additionally, only one resolution level is used (as we are interested to recover fine scale deformation details in this case). The wavelet analysis and the sparseness measure are the same as in the rigid deformation case and this assumption will be maintained in all the experiments in Sections 6.3, 6.4, 6.5 and 6.6. The behavior of the alignment against the B-spline grid spacing Δ_B will be analyzed in Section 6.3.

6 RESULTS

In order to test the proposed algorithm a series of experiments have been carried out in which we have used a set of 13 perfusion images. Its major features are summarized in Table 2.

All the images present a slice thickness of 10 mm and have been acquired with a Philips Intera 1.5 T scanner using a fast field echo MAG prepared gradient recalled sequence. A spatial presaturation has been applied in all cases except for the last one, which, in addition, uses a partial Fourier phase encoding. The flip angle has been of 50° except for the last case, in which it is of 15° .

The procedure of validation uses a manual segmentation of the myocardium in the medial slice from the

Fig. 4. Example of a first-pass cardiac perfusion acquisition. From top to bottom: apical, medial and basal slices. From left to right some samples of the perfusion dynamics are shown. In the first column the contrast has not reached the heart yet. In the second column the contrast has reached the right ventricle (RV) cavity. In the third one it has reached the LV cavity. In the fourth column the contrast partially reaches the myocardium whereas in the fifth the contrast has fully reached it and in the sixth the contrast starts to be washed out.

TABLE 2

Major features of the sample used for validation. Δ : resolution (mm). T_E : echo time (ms). T_R : repetition time (ms). f_s : heart rate (bpm).

Item	N	Δ	T_E	T_R	f_s
1	139	1.250	1.386	2.772	64
2	132	1.667	1.239	2.478	67
3	159	1.424	1.341	2.682	70
4	155	1.250	1.385	2.770	82
5	159	1.389	1.335	2.670	73
6	188	1.250	1.385	2.770	67
7	139	1.354	1.347	2.694	57
8	149	1.840	1.243	2.486	71
9	188	1.562	1.226	2.452	69
10	188	1.458	1.301	2.602	63
11	135	1.424	1.303	2.606	66
12	188	1.389	1.321	2.642	65
13	60	1.680	1.041	2.773	73

first time instant in the sequence in which the contrast is noticeable in the LV cavity (i.e., approximately the one corresponding to the third column in Fig. 4) to 32 subsequent time instants. The images are registered by different procedures and the segmented myocardium is transformed for each image with the transformation resulting from the registration. The Dice coefficient between the transformed segmentations for every pair of images in the sequence (so as to avoid bias) is used to evaluate the registration performance for a given pro-

cedure. The differences in performance are assessed by performing a set of two tailed t -tests with unknown and different variances between different pairs of registration procedures.

In all the experiments $10 \cdot 4^r$ iterations of a gradient descent procedure are used in the rigid registration case, with $r = 0$ for the finest resolution. Thus, the iterations are increased by a factor $I_R = 4$ between each resolution level, and $I = 10$ iterations are used for the finest resolution level. The step size for each level is of $500 \cdot 2^r$ mm for the displacement parameters (i.e. the center of rotation and the translation) and of $0.01 \cdot 2^r$ rad for the rotation parameter. Thus, a relative scaling of $c = 50000$ mm/rad is taken for the displacements with respect to the rotations, the step length increases a factor $S_R = 2$ between each resolution level, and a base step length of $S = 500$ mm is used for the finest resolution level. On the other hand, $I = 20$ iterations and a step length of $S = 5000$ mm are used in the elastic registration case. All the images are normalized to the range $[0, 1]$ prior to registration. The dilation radius for the ROI extraction has been set to $\rho = 24$ mm. Needless to say, the ROI extraction is used for all the registration alternatives included in the experiments in order to perform fair comparisons.

6.1 Validation of the groupwise approach

In this Section we validate the adoption of a groupwise approach for the problem at hand. To that end we have

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the alignment procedure. The snapshots show three cuts of the perfusion dataset: (1) a short axis slice, (2) and (3) the temporal evolution of two orthogonal short axis profiles which intersect approximately at the center of the LV.

compared three registration alternatives:

- **No registration** (None). This corresponds to applying the identity transformation to all the images in the sequence.
- **Pairwise monomodal registration** (Pairwise). This procedure registers all the images in the sequence with the last one by using a mean squares metric. The last image is selected as reference because it allows for a clear differentiation of the structures in the image (due to the fact that much of the contrast is already out of the tissues).
- **Groupwise monomodal registration** (Groupwise). This procedure performs a groupwise registration by using the metric in (3).

In this experiment we have used a centered rigid 2D transformation for both the pairwise and groupwise registration. Hence, the elastic component of the deformation is not considered (see Section 5).

Results are summarized in Table 3. Statistically significant differences are observed between the None and the Pairwise and between the Pairwise and Groupwise cases. Thus it can be inferred that a generic registration procedure is able to partially improve the alignment between the images and that a groupwise monomodal registration strategy further improves the alignment. Additionally, the distribution of Dice coefficients between each pair of registered images of the perfusion sequences is depicted in Fig. 6 by means of a violin-plot diagram, which includes a box-plot diagram (with outliers denoted by red markers and whiskers representing data at ± 2.7 std the mean value) and a kernel density plot (added to each side of the box-plot). Note in Fig. 6 the ability of the groupwise approach to limit the presence of outliers with respect to the pairwise counterpart. This fact is further confirmed by its smaller std (see Table 3).

TABLE 3

Results on the validation of the groupwise approach. The diagonal entries of the Table show the mean \pm std Dice coefficient between each pair of registered manual segmentations. The entries in the upper triangle of the Table show the p value of a two tailed t -test with unknown and different variances between the corresponding pairs of registration procedures. Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) are boldfaced.

Method	None	Pairwise	Groupwise
None	0.652 ± 0.217	$< \mathbf{10^{-9}}$	$< \mathbf{10^{-9}}$
Pairwise	—	0.741 ± 0.176	$< \mathbf{10^{-9}}$
Groupwise	—	—	0.764 ± 0.142

Fig. 6. Violin-plot on the validation of the groupwise approach: distribution of the Dice coefficients between each pair of registered manual segmentations.

Needless to say, the apparent absence of outliers for the None case is due to the much larger std of the Dice coefficients in this case, which hides the existence of misalignment of many images (as given by the outliers in the plot) by the whiskers of the box-plot.

6.2 Validation of the developed metric

In this Section we validate the developed metric for the groupwise registration approach. To that end we have compared the registration metrics proposed in the

Fig. 7. Violin-plot on the validation of the metric choice: distribution of the Dice coefficients between each pair of registered manual segmentations.

literature (see Section 3) with our proposal (see Section 4). Namely we have tested the following registration alternatives:

- **No registration** (None).
- **Variance of the intensities** (VI). This procedure uses the metric in (3). Thus it corresponds to the procedure named Groupwise in Section 6.1.
- **Entropy of the distribution of intensities** (EDI). This procedure uses the metric in (4). The parameter $\sigma = 0.05$ (see [29]) has been experimentally selected within the set $\{0.02, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6\}$ as the one that provides the largest mean Dice coefficient for this problem.
- **Variance of the local entropy** (VLE). This procedure uses the metric in (6). The radius of the neighborhood $r_{|\mathcal{N}|} = 6$ pix. and the number of bins $n_b = 12$ (see [30]) have been experimentally selected as the pair that provides the largest mean Dice coefficient for this problem from the sets $\{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8\}$ and $\{6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13\}$ respectively.
- **Sparsity-promoting** (SP). This procedure uses the metric proposed in Section 4 with the specific implementation presented in Section 5.

In this experiment we have also used a centered rigid 2D transformation, as in Section 6.1.

Results are summarized in Table 4. The best results are obtained by our SP metric and significant differences are observed among all pairs of metrics, which suggest that the metric choice is important for this application. Note also how the SP case has a much smaller std than the other metrics. This fact is further illustrated by the distribution of Dice coefficients between each pair of registered images of the perfusion sequences for each metric shown in Fig. 7: the results are clearly more robust with our metric than with any of the others so far proposed. Fig. 7 also provides information about the advantages and drawbacks of the metrics. Thus, though the EDI metric is ranked the second in terms of the mean precision, it seems more prone to the presence of outliers than the monomodal VI metric. On the other hand, the VLE metric ranks the last in terms of the mean precision (even below the VI metric).

6.3 Validation of the elastic transformation assumption

In this Section we validate the elastic transformation assumption. To that end we have compared the performance of the B-spline deformable transformation under different spacings of the grid Δ_B against the performance of the rigid transformation for the SP metric. The spacings are selected such that they cover the reasonable practical range of values for this parameter. Namely, they cover a range from approximately 2 to 15 times the resolution of the images. Seven registration alternatives are compared:

- **No registration** (None).
- **Rigid registration** (Rigid). This procedure uses the metric proposed in Section 4 with the specific implementation presented in Section 5 without correction of elastic motion. Thus it corresponds to the procedure named SP in Section 6.2.
- **Elastic registration A** ($\Delta_B = 3$ mm). This procedure (as well as the next ones) uses the SP metric proposed in Section 4 with the specific implementation presented in Section 5 with correction of elastic motion.
- **Elastic registration B** ($\Delta_B = 5$ mm).
- **Elastic registration C** ($\Delta_B = 9$ mm).
- **Elastic registration D** ($\Delta_B = 15$ mm).
- **Elastic registration E** ($\Delta_B = 23$ mm).

Results are summarized in Table 5. Statistically significant differences are observed between rigid and elastic registration. Thus it can be inferred that the groupwise sparsity-promoting elastic registration procedure is able to partially improve the alignment between the images with respect to the rigid counterpart. The best results are obtained with $\Delta_B = 15$ mm although without significant differences against the $\Delta_B = 9$ mm case, which indicates the stability of the registration result against small variations of the grid spacing. Additionally, the distribution of Dice coefficients between each pair of registered images of the perfusion sequences is depicted in Fig. 8, showing the ability of the elastic registration approach to diminish the influence of some of the outliers. Namely, the elastic registration is able to diminish the influence of those outliers that, nonetheless, present a relatively significant level of overlap of the myocardial segmentations after the rigid alignment. Unlike them, the outliers that present the lowest Dice coefficients (caused by an image in one of the patients corrupted by a weird acquisition artifact in which a white strip crosses the left ventricle) are too far to be aligned after the rigid registration that the elastic alignment is unable to improve the myocardial overlap.

6.4 Comparison of different registration alternatives

In this Section we compare different alternatives and parameter configurations to perform the alignment with our method. Namely, we study the results against the

TABLE 4

Results on the validation of the metric choice. The diagonal entries of the Table show the mean \pm std Dice coefficient between each pair of registered manual segmentations. The entries in the upper triangle of the Table show the p value of a two tailed t -test with unknown and different variances between the corresponding pairs of registration procedures. Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) are boldfaced.

Method	None	VI	EDI	VLE	SP
None	0.652 \pm 0.217	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$
VI	—	0.764 \pm 0.142	$4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$
EDI	—	—	0.782 \pm 0.128	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$
VLE	—	—	—	0.738 \pm 0.179	$< 10^{-9}$
SP	—	—	—	—	0.810 \pm 0.085

TABLE 5

Results on the validation of the elastic transformation assumption. The diagonal entries of the Table show the mean \pm std Dice coefficient between each pair of registered manual segmentations. The entries in the upper triangle of the Table show the p value of a two tailed t -test with unknown and different variances between the corresponding pairs of registration procedures. Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) are boldfaced.

Method	None	Rigid	$\Delta_B = 3$ mm	$\Delta_B = 5$ mm	$\Delta_B = 9$ mm	$\Delta_B = 15$ mm	$\Delta_B = 23$ mm
None	0.652 \pm 0.217	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$
Rigid	—	0.810 \pm 0.085	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$
$\Delta_B = 3$ mm	—	—	0.819 \pm 0.078	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$	$1 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$\Delta_B = 5$ mm	—	—	—	0.824 \pm 0.075	$4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.381
$\Delta_B = 9$ mm	—	—	—	—	0.828 \pm 0.071	0.866	0.035
$\Delta_B = 15$ mm	—	—	—	—	—	0.828 \pm 0.070	0.022
$\Delta_B = 23$ mm	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.825 \pm 0.070

Fig. 8. Violin-plot on the validation of the elastic transformation assumption: distribution of the Dice coefficients between each pair of registered manual segmentations.

number of decomposition levels (Section 6.4.1), the results of the use of different analysis wavelets (Section 6.4.2), and the influence of the parameter α of the Renyi entropy (Section 6.4.3).

6.4.1 Number of decomposition levels

Here we compare the relative performance of different choices for the number of decomposition levels for this application. The alternatives of using $J = 7$, $J = 6$ (default selection), $J = 5$, and $J = 4$ levels are compared. The results are summarized in Table 6. The best performance is obtained by the case $J = 6$ but without significant differences with respect to the case $J = 7$. This suggest that increasing the number of decomposition

Fig. 9. Violin-plot on the validation of the number of decomposition levels: distribution of the Dice coefficients between each pair of registered manual segmentations.

levels for $J \geq 6$ does not improve the performance, although it entails a computational overload. The cases $J = 5$ and $J = 4$ perform significantly worse than the cases $J = 7$ and $J = 6$. Additionally, the distribution of Dice coefficients between each pair of registered images of the perfusion sequences is depicted in Fig. 9, showing the ability of the cases $J = 5$, $J = 6$ and $J = 7$ to minimize the influence of the outliers.

6.4.2 Wavelet used for the analysis

Here we compare the relative performance of different wavelet analysis frames. Namely, we study the Daubechies wavelets family. Four decomposition frames are considered corresponding to the first (DB1), second (DB2, default selection), third (DB3) and fourth (DB4) order wavelets. The results are summarized in Table 7. The best results are obtained with the DB2 wavelet with significant differences with respect to the remaining

TABLE 6

Results on the validation of the number of decomposition levels. The diagonal entries of the Table show the mean \pm std Dice coefficient between each pair of registered manual segmentations. The entries in the upper triangle of the Table show the p value of a two tailed t -test with unknown and different variances between the corresponding pairs of registration procedures. Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) are boldfaced.

Method	$J = 7$	$J = 6$	$J = 5$	$J = 4$
$J = 7$	0.828 ± 0.072	0.775	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$
$J = 6$	—	0.828 ± 0.070	$< 10^{-9}$	$< 10^{-9}$
$J = 5$	—	—	0.797 ± 0.094	$< 10^{-9}$
$J = 4$	—	—	—	0.695 ± 0.182

Fig. 10. Violin-plot on the validation of the wavelet frame used for the analysis: distribution of the Dice coefficients between each pair of registered manual segmentations.

cases. The DB2 wavelet is suited to represent linear polynomials and therefore it is able to cope with the linear ramp of the perfusion signal as it gradually enters the tissues without much complexity, which could explain its good performance for this application. Additionally, the distribution of Dice coefficients between each pair of registered images of the perfusion sequences is depicted in Fig. 10, showing the ability of the DB2 wavelet to limit the negative influence of some of the outliers.

6.4.3 Free parameter of the Renyi entropy

We have conducted an experiment in which we study the influence of α in the results of the alignment. To that end we have performed the alignment with α ranging from 0.1 to 1.2 in steps of 0.1. The mean \pm std of the result is presented in Fig. 11. According to the theoretical discussion in Section 4, the best results are obtained for $\alpha = 0.4$ (just below $\alpha = 0.5$).

6.5 Visual results

In this Section we present some visual results of different outputs of the alignment procedure related to different registration methodologies. Namely, the results for the patient for which the alignment provides the largest improvement in the mean Dice coefficient are included in Fig. 12, whereas the results for the patient for which the smallest improvement is obtained are included in Fig. 13. We show the cases None, Pairwise and Groupwise of Section 6.1, the case SP of Section 6.2 and the case $\Delta_B = 15$ mm of Section 6.3. For a general visualization of the alignment, we show the temporal evolution of two orthogonal short axis profiles which intersect approximately at the center of the LV. First, the Pairwise

Fig. 11. Plot on the influence of the parameter α of the Renyi entropy.

case roughly aligns the whole sequence (see Fig. 12b). Second, the Groupwise provides a further alignment (see the cavity borders on the left column of Fig. 13c) though it presents some rough errors in the part of the sequence previous to the arrival of the contrast to the cavity (see for instance the right column of Fig. 13c). Third, the SP shows more clearly defined structures (see the cavity borders on the right column of Fig. 13d). Finally, the $\Delta_B = 15$ mm method proposed in this paper corrects for most of the remaining small misalignments in the sequence.

6.6 Computational complexity

Finally, regarding the computational complexity of the method, we have conducted the experiments on an 8xDual Core AMD Opteron(tm) Processor 885 at 2.6GHz (cache size of 1MB and shared memory of 16GB). Using the pairwise computation time as the base of comparison, one obtains that introducing any of the major assumptions of our framework (consecutively the groupwise approach, the sparsity-promoting metric and the elastic transformation) entails a ratio of computation times of 1 : 3.21 : 6.96 : 17.46, which seems affordable for most practical applications.

7 DISCUSSION

In this paper we have presented a methodology to design a new family of groupwise registration metrics

TABLE 7

Results on the validation of the wavelet frame used for the analysis. The diagonal entries of the Table show the mean \pm std Dice coefficient between each pair of registered manual segmentations. The entries in the upper triangle of the Table show the p value of a two tailed t -test with unknown and different variances between the corresponding pairs of registration procedures. Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) are boldfaced.

Method	DB1	DB2	DB3	DB4
DB1	0.821 ± 0.084	$4 \cdot 10^{-7}$	0.617	0.240
DB2	—	0.828 ± 0.070	$7 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$< 10^{-9}$
DB3	—	—	0.822 ± 0.072	0.070
DB4	—	—	—	0.819 ± 0.073

(a) None.

(b) Pairwise.

(c) Groupwise.

(d) SP.

(e) $\Delta_B = 15$ mm.

Fig. 12. Visual results on the alignment procedure for the best case. Note the progressive refinement of the alignment by introducing the major features of our approach.

for the alignment of a sequence of images of a natural phenomenon through time. Although we have applied this methodology to the alignment of cardiac MR perfusion images, it can also be applied to a large variety of problems provided that the aligned temporal curves are expected to have a sparse nature, which is a reasonable assumption for most physical phenomena. For instance, in medical imaging, the metric could be applied to other dynamic contrast-enhanced applications, to motion tracking in the presence of intensity changes through time [31] or even to the study of the development of a

(a) None.

(b) Pairwise.

(c) Groupwise.

(d) SP.

(e) $\Delta_B = 15$ mm.

Fig. 13. Visual results on the alignment procedure for the worst case. Note the progressive refinement of the alignment by introducing the major features of our approach.

pathology in follow-up studies. Additionally, according to its assumptions, the proposed methodology seems appropriate to object motion tracking under the presence of lightning changes, occlusions or framing variations.

It is interesting to note that our sparsity-promoting metric can be understood as a compromise between a pairwise sequential registration and a pure groupwise registration (i.e. one in which the order of the metric samples is not considered in the metric design). Thus it is expected to provide more flexibility than any of those extreme cases. Additionally, many possibilities

exist to generalize our work to build new metrics for other groupwise registration problems by resorting to the vast literature on wavelet analysis. For instance, one could resort to the use of overcomplete representations different from the UWT here proposed or to build specific dictionaries for the temporal signal to be recovered after the alignment. Additionally, let's recall that for the selection of a proper sparsity measure one must ensure the differentiability of the metric so that a common sparsity measure such as the L^1 -norm cannot be used for this problem due to its non-differentiable nature. This limitation of the L^1 -norm, as well as the use of an entropy measure, which is common in registration, has motivated the introduction of the Renyi entropy of the normalized coefficients of the wavelet decomposition as a measure of sparsity. Nevertheless, many different sparsity measures, either based on the entropy concept or not, could be used in the metric design (see [24], [25] for a thorough discussion on this issue, which largely exceeds the objectives of our proposal).

In Section 6 we have performed an extensive experimentation in order to prove the appropriateness of the main features of our approach for the alignment of cardiac MR perfusion images (namely, the adoption of a groupwise registration framework, the use of a sparsity-promoting metric and its insertion on an elastic transformation model of the deformation among the images). The idea behind this validation methodology has been to provide a general technical comparison of our approach with most of the alignment standard approaches proposed in the literature and to justify the suitability of our framework. Nevertheless, the clinical application of our method to perfusion quantification would require to analyze the perfusion curves obtained after the alignment in order to extract the physiological parameters related to perfusion from them [2]. This analysis can benefit from the smoother temporal curves, which can help improve its resolution detail, critical in the detection and quantification of subendocardial perfusion defects. For the sake of conciseness the perfusion analysis has not been included in this registration-oriented paper and will be a subject of further research.

Thus we have introduced a simple, flexible and easily extensible methodology for the alignment of images in which contrast varies in time. The extensions of our method could come from the adoption of different developments in the wavelet analysis literature or, perhaps of more interest for the analysis of cardiac MR perfusion sequences, from the adaptation of the analysis of the temporal signal to the expected behavior of the contrast uptake in different spatial locations of the image. Then, for instance, one could resort to a combined registration-segmentation approach as in [16] in order to further refine the results of the alignment. Additionally, in order to provide a comparison within a generic elastic registration framework, we have modeled the deformation by an Euclidean B-spline grid. Nevertheless, we think that it seems reasonable to adapt the grid to the geometry of

the myocardium (i.e., to adopt a polar coordinate system) in order to better adapt the deformation space to the underlying deformations to which the heart is actually subject.

8 CONCLUSION

In this paper we have proposed a framework for the alignment of sequences corresponding to time-dependent studies of a given physical phenomenon by considering the basic assumption that the temporal curves obtained after the alignment should have a sparse nature. The new metric introduced for this kind of problem, operating inside a groupwise registration approach, allows to cope with changes in the tissue contrast through time providing satisfactory results in recovering elastic deformations. This methodology has been applied to the alignment of cardiac MR perfusion sequences, where we have proved a statistically significant improvement in performance when including each of the major features of our framework.

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